
Investigating Government Effectiveness as a Determinant of Financial Crime

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Abstract

This study focused on ‘investigating government effectiveness as a determinant of financial crime’. One research question and one hypothesis guided the study. Works of literature pertinent to the study were reviewed. The population of 214 World Bank member countries as of the year 2021 also represents the sample. However, it was further stripped to 155 countries due to the absence of data for variables in some countries, which was refined by removing those countries from the sample. Data for the study were collected from the World Bank Governance Indicators (WGI). The level of financial crime data was mirrored using the control of corruption data. The year 2021, the most recent year available on the World Bank indicator database, was explored because the researcher sampled the total population, focusing on the global countries rather than comparing time series. The data were analysed, and all the results were computed using the R-studio. The results were tested using the regression analysis, including the t-test and the correlation coefficients, which were tested at a 0.05 level of significance to ensure solid evidence. Results of the study indicated that government effectiveness significantly influences financial crime and with a positive coefficient, which implies that the financial crime level increases as government effectiveness increases. This study recommends that, to effectively combat financial crime, policymakers should move beyond general measures of government effectiveness and adopt a more targeted, dual-pronged strategy.

Keywords: Government effectiveness, Financial crime, Anti-corruption, Public governance

1.0 Introduction

Global economies have, in the last several decades, witnessed an increased awareness of the threat financial crime activities such as fraud, cybercrime, money laundering, embezzlement, insider trading, counterfeiting, tax evasion, bribery, and terrorism financing pose to them. CFI (2023), in its elaborate listing of financial crime types, has categorized billing schemes, petty theft, payroll schemes, skimming from transactions, and using companies' funds for personal use as lesser financial crime activities. These activities have negative impacts on economies at different scales, and this has increased attention to the issue.

Alan (2018) suggests that not only are the long-term health of economies affected by financial crime, but their citizens also have their fair share, especially in the recent dispensation. While some individuals participate in financial crime for their gain, known as occupational crime, in corporate crime, corporations benefit when a financial crime is carried out says Bittle & Hebert, (2020).

The financial crime phenomenon is such a complex issue (Achim & Borlea, 2021), that its understanding, comprehension, and measurement remain complex and multi-faceted. (Hamid et al., 2013). Understanding the scale of financial crime is far-reaching since not all occurrences of financial crime, including fraud, embezzlement, and money laundering, are recognized, and recorded.

There are significant variations in the definition and collection of crime statistics between nations, as pointed out by Mrohorolu et al. (2006). Major discrepancies also exist in the ways that various nations report their data. However, estimates and valuations of the true cost or worth of financial crime have been made by experts. Heeks et al. (2018) made an official report to the Home Office, United Kingdom, on the estimated costs of fraud and cyber-crimes in the year 2018, which stood them at £4.7 billion and £1.1 billion, respectively, while an estimation of the global cost of financial crime compliance made by NexisLexis Risk Solutions (2021) stood at \$213.9 billion.

While the study of financial crime has grown over the years, little progress has been made in establishing the significance level of the relationship between financial crime determinants and their levels in countries. This study would contribute to this shortfall as it will investigate if a statistically significant relationship exists between an identified determinant of financial crime and financial crime level, having identified government effectiveness as a determinant variable, as outlined by Achim et al. (2021) for this study.

The problem this study tends to address has existed long before (Bucur, 2011) and has been studied by different researchers. Establishing what motivates or determines financial crime activities has been a concern.

While some researchers, such as Afonso & Rodrigues (2021), Avortri & Agbanyo (2020), have questioned whether high levels of crime/corruption can slow GDP growth, governance, and political stability, this study will flip the coin to investigate what contribution improved governance would make in the fight against financial crime. Good governance refers to the effective and responsible management of an organization or country and can be argued to serve as a deterrent to financial crime (Achim et al., 2021).

Research Question

This study tends to answer the following question:

Is there a significant relationship between level of governance effectiveness and financial crime in nations?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were derived from the research questions to enable the researcher to achieve the research aims and guide this study.

Null (H0): Government effectiveness does not have a statistically significant influence on financial crime.

Alternative (H1): Government effectiveness has a statistically significant influence on financial crime.

2.0 Literature Review

The Concept of Financial Crime

Financial crime is generally referred to as activities involving fraud, embezzlement, tax evasion, corruption, cybercrimes, theft, forgery, cheating, and counterfeiting (Achim & Borlea, 2021). While the definition Achim & Borlea (2021) gave provides a basic framework for understanding financial crime, the Financial Conduct Authority - FCA (2013) gave an outlined definition, grouping the activities into their characteristics, referred to it as any kind of criminal conduct relating to money or financial services or markets, including any offense involving: (a) fraud or dishonesty; or (b) misconduct in, or misuse of information relating to, a financial market; or (c) handling the proceeds of crime; or (d) the financing of terrorism. In this definition, FCA (2013) reiterated that "offense" includes an act or omission which would be an offense if it had taken place in the United Kingdom. Letia (2014) detailed representation of financial crime as a breach of trust, betraying the confidence of others by taking advantage of the perceived trustworthiness and stability of financial, commercial, and banking activities.

Financial crime is a serious problem that can have far-reaching effects on the economy and individuals, and it is important for individuals and organizations to be aware of these risks and take steps to protect themselves. Financial crime, its causes, and its consequences have been studied. The interest in financial crime has prompted scholars with varied intents and objectives to explore the phenomenon.

Exploring Government Effectiveness as a Determinant of Financial Crime

Effective governance involves clear laws and regulations, strong institutions, and effective oversight and accountability mechanisms (Bucur, 2011). Governance typically involves three major underlying variables: formulation of regulation, rule of law, and the legislative system (Bucur 2011, Letia 2014, Put 2015).

While the quality of regulation refers to the government's ability on the formulation and implementation of sustainable rules and policies, which in turn promotes both private and public sector growth. Bucur (2011), the rule of law typically means that everyone is subject to and equal before the law. Bucur (2011) agrees that a legislative system where inconsistent, unclear, and incomplete regulation/criminal law and fraud stimulation abound, making economic development unachievable even with a conducive environment fosters financial and economic crimes. Summarily, good governance can help to create a culture of integrity

and ethical behaviour within an organization or country, which can further reduce the likelihood of financial crime occurring (Achim & Borlea, 2021).

Various studies (Achim & Borlea, 2021; Wu, 2005; AlQudah et al., 2021), in their findings, found a positive relationship between government effectiveness and financial crime level, noting that the presence of effective governance reduces financial crime. Achim & Borlea (2021) conducted empirical research and found the existence of a significant influence of the level of government effectiveness and GDP growth on the financial crime and corruption level as these factors promoted economic development and financial freedom. Empirical results from the study by AlQudah et al. (2021) showed that public governance wholly moderates the level of criminal financial activities, like money laundering.

The result of a similar study by Achim & Borlea (2021) confirms that a high-quality credible financial system leads to a decrease in the volume of money laundering crimes. A financial system can be argued to be credible as an import of effective governance as both the credibility/reliability and stability of a financial environment are technically the outcome of governmental laws, policies, and regulations put in place.

As AlQudah et al. (2021) expressed, credible governance could reduce all illegal activities, including money laundering and financial crime. This is because it would ensure that the rule of law is upheld and that corruption is controlled.

While these studies are consistent with the Alternative hypothesis (H1) that guided this study which assumes that ‘government effectiveness has a statistically significant influence on financial crime’, the Null (H0) hypothesis that assumes that ‘government effectiveness does not have a statistically significant influence on financial crime’ was formed off the contradicting findings of Bucur (2011), Achim et al. (2021) and Caselli & Michaels (2013). This will enable the researcher to test whether the level of government effectiveness of economies statistically impacts the financial crime level, and its potential impacts on the occurrence and magnitude of financial crime.

Bucur (2011), in contrast to the findings of Achim & Borlea (2021), and AlQudah et al., (2021), found that the quality of regulations and the rule of law typically underpinning the level of governance effectiveness or ineffectiveness was found to be responsible for the growth of financial crime. This is arguably not surprising owing to a recent investigation by Achim et al. (2021), where the impact of economic development was matched with levels of financial crime, specifically cybercrime and money laundering in the EU member countries. The study revealed that while increased development produced a lower level of cybercrime, the same situation promoted money laundering. Similarly, Caselli & Michaels (2013) demonstrated in their study that a thriving economy borne by government effectiveness and economic growth generated an increased level of financial crime, corruption, and opportunities for extortion.

Researchers (Achim & Borlea 2021, Wu 2005, AlQudah et al. 2021, and Torgler & Schneider 2009) have found a statistically significant relation between governance effectiveness and financial crime with the level of crime lowering when government effectiveness improved. However, researchers like (Bucur 2011, Achim et al. 2021 and Caselli & Michaels 2013) in their study, produced a contradictory finding where improved governance, produces socio-economic development and a higher financial crime level, especially due to an increase in cash flow.

3.0 Methodology

This study used a quantitative research method, using secondary data from the World Bank Governance Indicators. The sample consisted of 155 countries, representing 71% of the total population. The year 2021 was chosen as it was the most recent year available on the World Bank indicator database, making it more representative of the current situation. The data was collected from the World Bank Governance Indicator, which provides the most up-to-date global development statistics. (World Bank, 2023) The World Bank calculates scores between -2.5 (weak) and 2.5 (strong). The data was analysed using R-studio, with descriptive statistics using mean, minimum, maximum, and standard deviation. Histograms were used to illustrate the statistical results. Results were tested using regression analysis, including the t-test and correlation coefficients, at a 0.05 level of significance to ensure solid evidence. The descriptive statistics summarize the data set used in the study, focusing on the mean, minimum, and maximum values of the variables under study.

Table 1 summarizes the variables used in the study, focusing more on the mean, minimum and maximum values of the variables understudy.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Mean	Min	Max	Std Deviation
Financial Crime Level	0.01	-1.61	2.37	0.99
Government Effectiveness	0.03	-2.19	2.00	0.98

The average financial crime level presents a mean of 0.01 which falls between the threshold of -2.5 and +2.5 of the World Governance Index (WGI) (World Bank, 2023), indicating a high financial crime. Also, a look at the minimum (Min) and maximum (Max) values shows that the data for financial crime level lies between -1.61 and 2.37, which further lends credence that the mean (0.01) as an indication of a downward trend in financial crime level in most of the sampled countries (Kalton & Conway, 2019). The standard deviation value of 0.99, which is significantly greater than the mean (0.01), is indicative of the fact that there is much variance in the data, that is, the observed data is quite spread out.

Concerning government effectiveness, a mean value of 0.03 indicates a largely positive trend in government effectiveness across the countries. The minimum (-2.19) and maximum (2.00) values mirror that some of the countries were faced with a low level of government effectiveness while others experience high government effectiveness, implying an unequal level of government effectiveness across the sampled countries. A standard deviation of 0.98, clearly evidences that the deviation from the sample mean (0.03) is high, which indicates much variance across the countries in terms of government effectiveness (Bickel & Lehman, 2019).

Assessing the Distributional Properties of the Data Using Histogram

Graphing the data associated with the sampled countries displays the distributional properties of the data as presented in the figures below:

Figure 1:

Figure 2:

The distributional properties of financial crime level and government effectiveness share similar features, as seen in Figures 1 and 2 respectively. The histograms of financial crime and government effectiveness demonstrate that the distribution has more negative than positive values, meaning that more of the sampled countries may have experienced a high level of financial crime due to the government's ineffectiveness. Also, with the distribution very close to the center (0), the distribution could be said to be roughly symmetrical.

Correlation Coefficient Analysis

The correlation between two variables is a proxy for the strength of their linear link. The table below displays the relationship between financial crime and government effectiveness. The Pearson correlation coefficient was utilized to ascertain the nature and direction of the link between the variables.

The correlation coefficient's values fall between -1 and 1. The absolute value of the correlation coefficient denotes the strength, with higher values indicating stronger links and lower values indicating weaker interactions (David, 2009). The sign of the correlation coefficient reflects the direction of the association (positive or negative). Each variable has a

perfect positive linear relationship with itself, resulting in correlation coefficients on the major diagonal of 1.0.

Table 2: Correlation Analysis

Variables	Correlation Coefficient
Financial Crime Level and Government Effectiveness	0.9075

The correlation coefficients show that the relationship among the variables was positive. First, the positive correlation coefficient (0.9075) between financial crime and government effectiveness indicates a strong positive relationship between financial crime and government effectiveness. This shows that the two variables increase and decrease simultaneously, that is, the two variables are strongly linked. The implication is that government effectiveness triggers financial crime and vice versa.

The correlation plot is depicted in Figure 3 below:

Figure 3: Plot of financial crime level against government effectiveness.

Figure 3 above demonstrates that the higher the correlation between the two variables, or the stronger the association, the more closely the data points resemble a straight line when plotted. The variables have a positive correlation if the data points form a straight line from close to the origin to high y-values, as shown by the correlation plots (David, 2009).

Multivariate Regression Analysis

A multivariate regression analysis explores the relationships between multiple independent variables and a single dependent variable (Frost, 2017). The controlling variables employed for the multi-regression model are political stability, GDP per capita (\$), inflation, and voice & accountability.

Multicollinearity Check

A multi-collinearity check was performed to validate the independent and controlling variables and ensure the validity and reliability of the regression analysis results.

Table 3: Multicollinearity Check Table

Variables	GDP per capita	Political Stability	Government Effectiveness	Inflation	Voice & Accountability.
Government Effectiveness	-0.04	0.27		0.06	0.10
Political Stability	0.02			-0.01	-0.07
GDP per capita (\$)				0.15	0.04
Inflation		-0.01			-0.13
Voice & Accountability					

Hint: independent variables cannot be checked against themselves, and the already checked ones may feature again in the table and are left blank since the result has been presented in previous boxes.

Multicollinearity is often indicated by an absolute correlation coefficient of >0.7 between two or more predictors (Gilbert, 2009). Since the correlation coefficients reported in Table 3 did not exceed 0.7 in any of the cases, the regression model is free from multicollinearity problems. As such, its results would be reliable.

The Multivariate Model

This study built two multivariate models, namely, the linear regression model and the log-linear regression model:

Financial crime level= f(government effectiveness, political stability, GDP per capita (\$), inflation, voice & accountability).

Econometrically:

Model 1:

Financial crime level= $\beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot \text{government effectiveness} + \beta_2 \cdot \text{political stability} + \beta_3 \cdot \text{GDP per capita } (\$) + \beta_4 \cdot \text{inflation} + \beta_5 \cdot \text{voice \& accountability}$.

Model 2:

(log) Financial crime level= $\beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot \text{government effectiveness} + \beta_2 \cdot \text{political stability} + \beta_3 \cdot \text{GDP per capita } (\$) + \beta_4 \cdot \text{inflation} + \beta_5 \cdot \text{voice \& accountability}$.

These two models were built to determine the best-fitting equation that describes the linear relationship between government effectiveness and financial crime level (Frost, 2017). The regression outcome demonstrates how each independent variable affected the dependent variable (Roback & Legler, 2016). The regression coefficient values, which vary from 0% to 100%, show how much of an impact there is (Frost, 2017). The F statistics, R-squared, and Adjusted R-squared of the models were compared, and the best model was selected based on the results.

Table 4: Linear Regression Model (Model 1) and Log-Linear Regression Model (Model 2)

Independent variable	Model 1 (Linear)	Model 2 (Log-linear)
Government effectiveness	0.0920***	1.0480***
Political stability	-0.0007	0.0100
GDP per capita (\$)	0.000*	0.0000
R-squared	0.8312	0.473
Adjusted R-squared	0.8256	0.4319
F-statistics	148.7	11.49
P-value (F-statistics)	0.000***	0.000***

Hint - Significance level: 0 ‘***’ 0.001 ‘**’ 0.01 ‘*’ 0.05 ‘.’ 0.1 ‘ ’ 1

- For this study, the researcher adopted a 5% level of significance.

Table 4 above presents the linear and log-linear regression coefficient estimates, respectively. The optimal or best model is selected based on the Adjusted R-squared and F-statistic values that evaluate how accurately a statistical model can forecast a result (Frost, 2017). Hence, the linear regression model (Model 1), which presented the highest Adjusted R-squared of 0.8256 and an F-statistic of 148.7 (compared to the log-linear model), was selected for the hypotheses testing.

Robustness Check

The evidence of heteroscedasticity or homoscedasticity during the robustness check will determine the acceptability and reliability of the multivariate model results (Roback & Legler, 2016). Heteroscedasticity tests are used to detect the presence of heteroscedasticity in a regression model and to assess the validity of the assumption of constant variance of errors. Homoscedasticity implies that the variability of errors is consistent and does not systematically change with the values of the independent variable(s). Homoscedasticity is an important assumption in linear regression, as violations of this assumption can affect the accuracy and reliability of the statistical inferences drawn from the model (Achim & Borlea, 2020).

The Breusch-Pagan Test

The Breusch-Pagan test, a widely used test for heteroscedasticity (Frost, 2017), was adopted for this study.

The below hypotheses were used to check for robustness and to determine if the model is statistically adequate.

H0: There is homoscedasticity

H1: There is heteroscedasticity

Table 5: The Breusch-Pagan test

	BP	df	p-value
Model 1	5.7107	5	0.3354

Table 5 above presents the result of the Breusch-Pagan heteroscedasticity test, evidencing that the model is free from significant heteroscedasticity as shown by the *Breusch-Pagan test p-value of 0.3354, greater than 0.05, informing the acceptance of the residuals as homoscedastic*. In line with this, the null hypothesis (H0) is accepted, validating ‘there is homoscedasticity’.

4.0 Discussion of findings

Government effectiveness turned out with a positive and statistically significant estimated coefficient. This means that an increase in government effectiveness leads to an increase in the level of financial crime.

From the regression coefficients, it can be adduced that the relationship between government effectiveness and financial crime was positive and statistically significant. This implies that higher government effectiveness increases the level of financial crime.

Hypotheses Testing: For this study, the coefficient and the p-value of the regression model was considered. For instance, if the probability value is less than 0.05, the variable is adjudged significant, and vice versa if the p-value is greater than 0.05.

Hypotheses:

Null (H0): Government effectiveness does not have a statistically significant influence on financial crime.

Alternative (H1): Government effectiveness has a statistically significant influence on financial crime.

Given that the coefficient of government effectiveness is positive, and its p-value equals $0 < 0.05$, it was concluded that the financial crime level increased significantly in the face of higher government effectiveness. Hence, the null hypothesis was rejected, and the alternative hypothesis was accepted. This is not in line with the expectation that government effectiveness should help reduce the rate of financial crime around the globe (AlQudah et al., 2021; Torgler & Schneider, 2009).

This result indicates that governance effectiveness which reflects a better quality of public and civil service, policy formulation and implementation (Bucur, 2011), and the credibility of government commitment to effective leadership (Put, 2015), caused a substantial increase in the level of financial crime. However, one can argue that the governance system has been ineffective in deploying measures to curtail financial misappropriation, enforce laws that would deter illegal financial activities, and punish criminal offenders. Elgin & Erturk (2019) and PWC (2018) substantiated this where they suggest that government effectiveness may not always deliver immediate sustainable socio-economic development and an enriched standard of living, a business-friendly environment, and better compliance with regulations, policies, and laws which automatically promote financial crime.

This result can also imply that as countries' government effectiveness level increases, there exists a possible increase in robust regulatory and enforcement mechanisms (Achim & Borlea, 2021), which may result in greater detection and reporting of financial crimes (Bucur, 2011). As a result, arguably, higher government effectiveness may lead to more effective measures in detecting and addressing financial crimes, leading to higher reported levels of financial crime. Government effectiveness may reflect stronger economic and financial systems, attracting more financial activities and transactions, and creating opportunities for financial crimes (Achim et al., 2021).

In line with the finding of this study, Bucur (2011), Achim et al. (2021) and Caselli & Michaels (2013) in their empirical findings demonstrated that government effectiveness triggered financial crime because of the high level of funds mobilization and investments in the public and private sectors which attracted financial crime activities aimed at the criminals aiming to have a share of the funds available.

5.0 Conclusion

This study explored government effectiveness as a financial crime determinant, to bring new solutions/approaches to the problem, due to the complexity of the manifestation forms of financial crime phenomena.

Based on the objective, which seeks to investigate the relationship between government effectiveness and the level of financial crime in all World Bank member countries for the year 2021, the study found that government effectiveness did not reduce the level of financial crime in 2021. With this finding, it can be said that government effectiveness did not reduce global financial crime in 2021.

This unexpected result (AlQudah et al., 2021; Torgler & Schneider, 2009) is attributed to the fact that government effectiveness may reflect stronger economic and financial systems, attracting more financial activities and transactions, and creating opportunities for financial crimes (Achim et al., 2021). In addition, arguably, higher government effectiveness may lead to more effective measures in detecting and addressing financial crimes, leading to higher reported levels of financial crime and, according to Bucur (2011), may result in greater detection and reporting of financial crimes due to increase in robust regulatory and enforcement mechanisms (Achim & Borlea, 2021).

6.0 Recommendation

This study recommends that to effectively combat financial crime, policymakers should move beyond general measures of government effectiveness and adopt a more targeted, dual-pronged strategy. This includes breaking down government effectiveness into specific components like regulatory quality and bureaucratic competence to identify their unique impacts on financial crime. In parallel, they should invest in advanced analytics to differentiate between increased detection and actual crime growth. Strong governance must be complemented with focused anti-crime tools such as specialized task forces, enhanced cross-border cooperation, and real-time monitoring. Finally, transparency, accountability, and context-specific reforms are essential to ensure institutional strength translates into meaningful proactive financial crime prevention, not just post-incident detection, in a complex, global financial environment.

References

- Achim, M. V., & Borlea, S. N. (2021). Economic and political determinants of economic and Financial Crime. *Economic and Financial Crime: Corruption, Shadow Economy, and Money Laundering*, 9(4), 71.
- Achim, M. V., Văidean, V. L., Borlea, S. N., & Florescu, D. R. (2021). The impact of the development of society on economic and financial crime. Case Study for European Union Member States. *Risks*, 9(5), 97.
- Afonso, A., & Rodrigues, de S. F. L. (2021). Corruption and economic growth: does the size of the government matter? *Economic Change and Restructuring*, 55, 543–576.
- AlQudah, A., Bani-Mustafa, A., Nimer, K., Alqudah, A. D., & AboElsoud, M. E. (2021). The effects of public governance and national culture on money laundering: A structured equation modeling approach. *Journal of Public Affairs*, 1(1).
- Asghar, N., Qureshi, S., & Nadeem, M. N. (2016). Effects of socio-economic and political factors on the crime rate in Pakistan. *Journal of Political Studies*, 23(1), 183:201.
- Avortri, C., & Agbanyo, R. (2020). Determinants of management fraud in the banking sector of Ghana: the perspective of the diamond fraud theory. *Journal of Financial Crime*, 28, 142–155.
- Bickel, P. J., & Lehmann, E. L. (2019). Descriptive statistics for nonparametric models. *The Annals of Statistics*, 3(5), 1038–1044.
- Bittle, S., & Hebert, J. (2020). Controlling corporate crimes in times of de-regulation and re-regulation. *He Handbook of White-Collar Crime, First Edition*, 30, 484–501.
- Bucur, D. (2011). *Cross-border crime and the globalized economy*. Bucharest: Pro Universitaria Publishing House.
- Byukoglu, B., Sit, A., & Eksi, I. (2021). Governance matters on non-performing loans: Evidence from emerging markets. *PSL Quarterly Review*, 74(296).
- CFI. (2023). *Financial crime risk management*. Corporate Finance Institute.
- David, F. N. (2009). *Tables of the ordinates and probability integral of the distribution of the correlation coefficient in small samples*. Cambridge University Press.
- De Rosa, D., Gooroochurn, N., & Gorg, H. (2010). Corruption and productivity: firm-level evidence from the BEEPS Survey. *Policy Research Working Paper, World Bank*, 5348.
- Elgin, C., & Erturk, F. (2019). Informal economies around the world: measures, determinants and consequences. *Eurasian Economic Review*, 9(2), 221–237.
- FCA. (2013). *FCA Handbook - FCA Handbook*. Fca.org.uk.
<https://www.handbook.fca.org.uk/handbook>
- Frost, J. (2017, July 27). *Model specification: Choosing the correct regression model - statistics By Jim*. Statistics by Jim.
- Gilbert, C. L. (2009). The diagnosis of multicollinearity. *Oxford Bulletin of Economics and Statistics*, 40(2), 87–91. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-0084.1978.mp40002001.x>
- Goel, R. K., & Ram, R. (2013). Economic uncertainty and corruption: evidence from a large cross-country data set. *Applied Economics*, 45(24), 3462–3468.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/00036846.2012.714073>
- Hamid, B. A., Habibullah, M. S., & Noor, Z. M. (2013). Crime and its socio-macroeconomics determinants: a panel-error-correct cointegration analysis. *UKM Journal Article Repository*, 47(2), 13–24.
- Heeks, M., Reed, S., Tafsiri, M., & Prince, S. (2018). *The economic and social costs of crime Second edition*.
https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/732110/the-economic-and-social-costs-of-crime-horr99.pdf
- IMF. (2020). *Higher Growth. Lower Crime?* International Monetary Fund.

- <https://www.imf.org/en/Blogs/Articles/2020/02/24/blog-higher-growth-lower-crime>
Kalton, G., & Conway, F. (2019). Descriptive statistics. *Applied Statistics*, 12(3), 195.
<https://doi.org/10.2307/2985799>
- Lafree, G., & Tseloni, A. (2006). Democracy and crime: A multilevel analysis of homicide trends in forty-four countries, 1950-2000. *The ANNALS of the American Academy of Political and Social Science*, 605(1), 25–49.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0002716206287169>
- Leția, A. A. (2014). *Investigation of business crime: money laundering, corruption and tax fraud, theoretical and practical aspects*. Universul Juridic Publishing House, Bucharest, Romania.
- NexisLexis Risk Solutions. (2021). *True cost of financial crime compliance study global report*. LexisNexis Risk Solutions. <https://risk.lexisnexis.com/global/en/insights-resources/research/true-cost-of-financial-crime-compliance-study-global-report>
- PWC. (2018). *Forensics*. PricewaterhouseCoopers.
<https://www.pwc.com/gx/en/services/forensics.html>
- Roback, P., & Legler, J. (2016). *Beyond multiple linear regression: Applied generalized linear models and multilevel models in R*. CRC Press LLC.
- Rodgers, P. A., & Yee, J. (2018). *The Routledge companion to design research*. Routledge/Taylor & Francis Group.
- Torgler, B., & Schneider, F. G. (2007). The impact of tax morale and institutional quality on the shadow economy. *SSRN Electronic Journal*, 30(3), 228–245.
<https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.958248>
- Wahl, I., Kastlunger, B., & Kirchler, E. (2010). Trust in authorities and power to enforce tax compliance: An empirical analysis of the “Slippery Slope Framework.” *Law & Policy*, 32(4), 383–406. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-9930.2010.00327.x>
- World Bank. (2023). *Data Bank | The World Bank*. Worldbank.org.
<https://databank.worldbank.org/>
- WU, X. (2005). Corporate governance and corruption: A cross-country analysis. *Governance*, 18(2), 151–170. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-0491.2005.00271.x>
- Yamen, A., Al Qudah, A., Badawi, A., & Bani-mustafa, A. (2019). The impact of national culture on financial crime. *Journal of Money Laundering Control*, 22(2).
<https://doi.org/10.1108/jmlc-01-2018-0004>

Appendix

Data collected and refined for analysis.

No	Year	Country Name	Country Code	Control of Corruption (Financial Crime Level)	Government Effectiveness	Political Stability	GDP per capita (\$)	Inflation	Voice & Accountability
1	2021	Albania	ALB	-0.555924177	-0.00336	0.109446	6492.872	2.04147	0.09120497
2	2021	Algeria	DZA	-0.614184439	-0.62076	-0.87647	3690.628	7.22606	-1.0095193
3	2021	Angola	AGO	-0.655345798	-1.05937	-0.71084	1953.534	25.7543	-0.840916
4	2021	Antigua and Barbuda	ATG	0.26372695	-0.14225	0.955552	15781.4	2.063	0.73925132
5	2021	Armenia	ARM	0.072149873	-0.24956	-0.83559	4966.513	7.18484	0.05920416
6	2021	Australia	AUS	1.73749423	1.51293	0.850989	60443.11	2.86391	1.3794421
7	2021	Austria	AUT	1.271236777	1.57001	0.914891	53637.71	2.76667	1.3985666
8	2021	Azerbaijan	AZE	-0.827584863	0.24768	-0.85348	5387.998	6.6503	-1.5304976
9	2021	Bahamas, The	BHS	1.181445718	0.4618	0.876719	27478.39	2.90491	0.91377217
10	2021	Bahrain	BHR	0.168159813	0.71713	-0.50511	26562.97	-0.60632	-1.5015956
11	2021	Bangladesh	BGD	-0.962003231	-0.62741	-0.97016	2457.925	5.54565	-0.7696443
12	2021	Belarus	BLR	-0.23533681	-0.77082	-0.73661	7302.258	9.46028	-1.5838302
13	2021	Belgium	BEL	1.484489679	1.12509	0.612555	51247.01	2.44025	1.28270888
14	2021	Belize	BLZ	-0.304920167	-0.48897	0.460717	6228.267	3.23564	0.55050194
15	2021	Benin	BEN	-0.154652014	-0.20667	-0.30134	1319.155	1.73354	-0.2375402
16	2021	Bhutan	BTN	1.553735256	0.79633	0.973133	3266.365	7.34684	0.22564517
17	2021	Bolivia	BOL	-0.86410296	-0.73192	-0.31857	3345.197	0.73738	-0.1099207
18	2021	Bosnia and Herzegovina	BIH	-0.643698514	-1.04125	-0.38058	7143.311	1.98164	-0.3133234
19	2021	Botswana	BWA	0.685204029	0.35407	0.978378	6805.221	7.24098	0.45758614
20	2021	Brazil	BRA	-0.477816075	-0.46029	-0.48501	7507.161	8.30166	0.2781969
21	2021	Brunei Darussalam	BRN	1.246438384	1.45483	1.168644	31449.08	1.73341	-0.8482108
22	2021	Bulgaria	BGR	-0.235711768	-0.13918	0.458269	12221.5	3.29774	0.29090291
23	2021	Burkina Faso	BFA	-0.059376009	-0.72633	-1.63874	893.0772	3.65353	-0.1093084
24	2021	Burundi	BDI	-1.580753326	-1.33109	-1.36398	221.4777	8.40454	-1.4051549
25	2021	Cabo Verde	CPV	1.035422206	0.04274	0.902458	3293.233	1.86215	0.9390173
26	2021	Cambodia	KHM	-1.176956654	-0.42264	-0.13212	1625.235	2.92073	-1.4358532
27	2021	Cameroon	CMR	-1.09271419	-0.87531	-1.40651	1666.933	2.27186	-1.1601563
28	2021	Canada	CAN	1.64609468	1.60389	0.936903	51987.94	3.39519	1.45788443
29	2021	Central African Republic	CAF	-1.226334929	-1.64427	-2.10454	461.1375	4.25936	-1.195578
30	2021	Chad	TCD	-1.477722049	-1.42402	-1.33554	685.6903	-0.77284	-1.4201199
31	2021	Chile	CHL	0.98372668	0.62607	0.062637	16265.1	4.52457	0.96785426
32	2021	China	CHN	0.053693742	0.84067	-0.48186	12556.33	0.98102	-1.6365763
33	2021	Colombia	COL	-0.344050169	-0.01456	-0.91408	6104.137	3.49506	0.09971508
34	2021	Congo, Rep.	COG	-1.37306428	-1.5511	-0.60662	2290.383	1.71564	-1.2380776
35	2021	Costa Rica	CRI	0.495704889	0.25731	0.872773	12472.44	1.72648	1.09140074
36	2021	Cote d'Ivoire	CIV	-0.371892631	-0.50191	-0.95286	2549.041	4.09195	-0.4710795
37	2021	Croatia	HRV	0.061275687	0.59104	0.707874	17685.33	2.55451	0.60984164
38	2021	Cyprus	CYP	0.394521177	0.73613	0.443114	31551.82	2.44609	0.86566663

39	2021	Czech Republic	CZE	0.641104996	1.11025	0.957601	26821.25	3.83984	1.01879382
40	2021	Denmark	DNK	2.366175175	2.00407	0.949907	68007.76	1.85305	1.55789542
41	2021	Dominican Republic	DOM	-0.569274545	0.031	0.137411	8476.752	8.243	0.30179748
42	2021	Ecuador	ECU	-0.573393404	-0.20915	-0.26625	5965.133	0.13325	0.10613444
43	2021	Egypt, Arab Rep.	EGY	-0.684838116	-0.43211	-1.02421	3698.835	5.21405	-1.5097785
44	2021	El Salvador	SLV	-0.532646835	-0.31268	-0.21123	4551.185	3.46693	-0.0552323
45	2021	Estonia	EST	1.535825491	1.38256	0.755604	27943.7	4.65317	1.19077373
46	2021	Ethiopia	ETH	-0.397181958	-0.61324	-2.06836	925.0774	26.8395	-1.0691051
47	2021	Fiji	FJI	0.47165674	0.62381	0.667942	4646.613	0.15586	-0.1503408
48	2021	Finland	FIN	2.270076752	1.96044	0.981908	53654.75	2.19457	1.62274849
49	2021	France	FRA	1.310407043	1.26752	0.371734	43658.98	1.64233	1.11508608
50	2021	Gambia, The	GMB	-0.358450145	-0.63848	0.175201	772.1524	7.37035	-0.1028912
51	2021	Georgia	GEO	0.688035369	0.65421	-0.42343	5023.274	9.56691	0.01531827
52	2021	Germany	DEU	1.813231826	1.33115	0.755996	51203.55	3.14297	1.43199122
53	2021	Ghana	GHA	-0.106090412	-0.14948	0.066448	2363.299	9.97109	0.46734911
54	2021	Greece	GRC	0.207244009	0.44355	0.154484	20192.6	1.22383	0.95542896
55	2021	Grenada	GRD	0.523264706	0.02653	1.04173	9010.572	1.21951	0.73408788
56	2021	Guatemala	GTM	-1.173671126	-0.75177	-0.39217	5025.542	4.26105	-0.4618636
57	2021	Guinea	GIN	-0.996127367	-0.91567	-0.97041	1189.176	12.5971	-0.9875714
58	2021	Guinea-Bissau	GNB	-1.300152063	-1.42388	-0.28024	795.1186	2.24249	-0.2363185
59	2021	Guyana	GUY	-0.165203333	-0.23673	-0.1438	9998.544	5.03286	0.24670784
60	2021	Haiti	HTI	-1.423377037	-2.18749	-1.09535	1829.593	16.8415	-0.9521484
61	2021	Honduras	HND	-1.072395802	-0.78213	-0.612	2771.717	4.48088	-0.5871212
62	2021	Hong Kong SAR, China	HKG	1.709560752	1.52612	0.261169	49800.54	1.56876	-0.211014
63	2021	Hungary	HUN	0.035607804	0.63451	0.861372	18728.12	5.11097	0.40406024
64	2021	Iceland	ISL	1.790595531	1.63863	1.373475	68727.64	4.44424	1.37459934
65	2021	India	IND	-0.294859201	0.28236	-0.61504	2256.59	5.13141	0.11272161
66	2021	Indonesia	IDN	-0.427905589	0.37901	-0.50647	4332.709	1.56013	0.15521753
67	2021	Iran, Islamic Rep.	IRN	-1.096301556	-0.85807	-1.62163	4091.209	43.389	-1.4702708
68	2021	Iraq	IRQ	-1.250528455	-1.29181	-2.39699	4775.377	6.04186	-0.9629664
69	2021	Ireland	IRL	1.649120331	1.50441	0.856822	100172.1	2.35814	1.43021321
70	2021	Israel	ISR	0.855771303	1.29197	-1.06135	52170.71	1.49229	0.68261665
71	2021	Italy	ITA	0.542555928	0.3612	0.578434	35657.5	1.87378	1.09520352
72	2021	Jamaica	JAM	-0.029271552	0.41401	0.223474	5183.581	5.86278	0.62797612
73	2021	Japan	JPN	1.565421462	1.40276	1.027348	39312.66	-0.23335	1.07693446
74	2021	Jordan	JOR	0.05046254	0.2274	-0.27573	4103.259	1.34609	-0.7991566
75	2021	Kenya	KEN	-0.713267028	-0.32999	-1.08966	2081.8	6.11091	-0.3662771
76	2021	Korea, Rep.	KOR	0.759860098	1.40621	0.662571	34997.78	2.49833	0.9311831
77	2021	Kosovo	XKX	-0.318530053	-0.22341	-0.12038	5269.784	3.35369	-0.079332
78	2021	Kyrgyz Republic	KGZ	-1.124733806	-0.72709	-0.42594	1276.7	11.905	-0.6054688
79	2021	Lao PDR	LAO	-1.03965342	-0.61772	0.726246	2535.623	3.75562	-1.6816999
80	2021	Latvia	LVA	0.746790171	0.87274	0.687567	21148.16	3.27583	0.90630883

81	2021	Lebanon	LBN	-1.22970438	-1.28704	-1.49348	4136.146	154.756	-0.6256257
82	2021	Lesotho	LSO	-0.315276623	-0.91377	-0.21959	1094.098	6.04775	-0.0198031
83	2021	Lithuania	LTU	0.851239979	1.05661	0.81543	23723.34	4.68354	1.04088652
84	2021	Luxembourg	LUX	1.871590853	1.71904	1.20638	133590.1	2.52692	1.5082804
85	2021	Madagascar	MDG	-0.933383822	-1.00036	-0.63593	500.511	5.81225	-0.2700881
86	2021	Malaysia	MYS	0.170527324	0.99169	0.138853	11109.26	2.4771	-0.1547223
87	2021	Maldives	MDV	-0.371216476	0.3864	0.502794	10366.29	0.54315	-0.2384848
88	2021	Mali	MLI	-0.867007017	-1.22319	-2.35244	873.7949	3.9256	-0.7774898
89	2021	Malta	MLT	0.31758076	0.89264	0.972676	33486.67	1.49789	1.08168638
90	2021	Mauritania	MRT	-0.821054399	-0.73372	-0.67025	2166.047	3.56516	-0.7652194
91	2021	Mauritius	MUS	0.467553556	0.8494	0.85581	9106.237	4.02853	0.66472882
92	2021	Mexico	MEX	-1.001628876	-0.31216	-0.63674	10045.68	5.68921	-0.0741874
93	2021	Moldova	MDA	-0.447890878	-0.40499	-0.20552	5230.662	5.10641	0.04762687
94	2021	Mongolia	MNG	-0.528645813	-0.46718	0.654302	4566.14	7.35281	0.3188701
95	2021	Montenegro	MNE	-0.019546321	0.00613	-0.14892	9465.704	2.4108	0.17449017
96	2021	Morocco	MAR	-0.433994025	-0.06678	-0.39608	3795.38	1.40196	-0.607271
97	2021	Mozambique	MOZ	-0.811555684	-0.76534	-1.22819	491.8391	5.68849	-0.6125438
98	2021	Namibia	NAM	0.258660823	0.05935	0.547819	4865.558	3.61691	0.57228744
99	2021	Nepal	NPL	-0.530735135	-0.87153	-0.24301	1208.219	4.08791	-0.0891101
100	2021	Netherlands	NLD	2.035641909	1.76668	0.915173	57767.88	2.67572	1.50255418
101	2021	New Zealand	NZL	2.201695204	1.35075	1.438624	48781.03	3.94112	1.62185359
102	2021	Nicaragua	NIC	-1.236290574	-0.8523	-0.46714	2045.535	4.92841	-1.2870005
103	2021	Niger	NER	-0.546674609	-0.61456	-1.6163	590.6295	3.83787	-0.3871441
104	2021	Nigeria	NGA	-1.070116878	-0.996	-1.7793	2065.749	16.9528	-0.6365556
105	2021	North Macedonia	MKD	-0.351957202	-0.08426	0.124912	6694.641	3.23075	0.14148904
106	2021	Norway	NOR	2.14091754	1.83936	1.103745	89154.28	3.48388	1.75175452
107	2021	Oman	OMN	0.086335801	-0.11808	0.506666	19509.47	1.54664	-1.1929884
108	2021	Pakistan	PAK	-0.785676658	-0.40269	-1.66678	1505.01	9.49621	-0.8405113
109	2021	Palau	PLW	-0.428823858	-0.2777	0.950392	12083.89	2.61248	1.05862057
110	2021	Panama	PAN	-0.570509851	0.1594	0.285786	14617.6	1.6307	0.54977256
111	2021	Papua New Guinea	PNG	-0.755582631	-0.88746	-0.58185	2672.946	4.48359	0.02295998
112	2021	Paraguay	PRY	-1.007155418	-0.62293	-0.00299	5891.5	4.78798	0.00905482
113	2021	Peru	PER	-0.63322556	-0.26079	-0.40597	6621.574	4.27166	0.18160866
114	2021	Philippines	PHL	-0.508519769	0.07033	-0.92892	3460.531	3.92718	-0.1504983
115	2021	Poland	POL	0.572010398	0.29278	0.51243	17999.91	5.05503	0.58724451
116	2021	Portugal	PRT	0.768555641	0.99131	0.952886	24567.51	1.26566	1.2580446
117	2021	Qatar	QAT	0.806125164	1.11364	0.95788	66838.36	2.30447	-1.1749094
118	2021	Romania	ROU	-0.037915125	-0.12964	0.533032	14858.23	5.05233	0.6020245
119	2021	Russian Federation	RUS	-0.900473714	-0.1761	-0.64544	12194.78	6.69446	-1.1018852
120	2021	Rwanda	RWA	0.599220455	0.26119	0.170439	822.348	-0.39135	-0.9554023
121	2021	Samoa	WSM	0.625925839	0.44313	1.109918	3857.318	3.1332	0.72614974
122	2021	Saudi Arabia	SAU	0.306925714	0.49631	-0.58386	23185.87	3.06329	-1.5906439
123	2021	Serbia	SRB	-0.437255442	0.04743	-0.13423	9230.178	4.0851	-0.1236479
124	2021	Sierra Leone	SLE	-0.431214958	-1.11451	-0.16455	480.0392	11.874	-0.0636349

125	2021	Singapore	SGP	2.171539545	2.29149	1.49319	72794	2.30486	-0.136062
126	2021	Slovak Republic	SVK	0.235205427	0.52921	0.559577	21391.93	3.14961	0.91435641
127	2021	Slovenia	SVN	0.71923095	1.1782	0.760044	29291.4	1.91707	0.91466957
128	2021	Solomon Islands	SLB	-0.140978411	-0.91164	0.490975	2304.845	-0.11544	0.46907106
129	2021	South Africa	ZAF	0.022103222	-0.01744	-0.70658	7055.045	4.61167	0.78849739
130	2021	Spain	ESP	0.741642237	0.94727	0.579051	30103.51	3.09314	1.010028
131	2021	Sri Lanka	LKA	-0.334563583	-0.08303	-0.31793	4013.688	7.01478	-0.0696102
132	2021	St. Kitts and Nevis	KNA	0.438981831	0.41732	0.955552	18082.61	1.19569	0.78219742
133	2021	St. Lucia	LCA	0.586345255	-0.09064	0.853993	9414.226	2.4107	0.86482322
134	2021	St. Vincent and the Grenadines	VCT	0.803943515	0.30754	1.04173	8666.387	1.57273	0.87782824
135	2021	Sudan	SDN	-1.289687276	-1.6375	-1.93504	751.8214	382.816	-1.4681702
136	2021	Suriname	SUR	-0.396517456	-0.64507	0.374922	4869.134	59.1117	0.37689281
137	2021	Sweden	SWE	2.130344868	1.65234	1.034035	61028.74	2.1632	1.50559938
138	2021	Switzerland	CHE	1.989697456	2.03225	1.131445	91991.6	0.58181	1.55418313
139	2021	Tanzania	TZA	-0.355093211	-0.63178	-0.43697	1099.288	3.69092	-0.7116134
140	2021	Thailand	THA	-0.45705694	0.25308	-0.54578	7066.191	1.2304	-0.7905759
141	2021	Tonga	TON	-0.384434402	0.28339	1.074102	4426.001	5.64051	0.72931576
142	2021	Trinidad and Tobago	TTO	-0.277760476	0.19269	0.154863	16032.5	2.05923	0.67239875
143	2021	Tunisia	TUN	-0.229555964	-0.16706	-0.69575	3807.139	5.70635	0.18709853
144	2021	Turkiye	TUR	-0.385957003	-0.0866	-1.09809	9661.236	19.5965	-0.8591428
145	2021	Uganda	UGA	-0.998556554	-0.57023	-0.85966	883.892	2.20457	-0.8217646
146	2021	Ukraine	UKR	-0.766656518	-0.40897	-1.09882	4835.572	9.36314	0.07631124
147	2021	United Kingdom	GBR	1.670565367	1.27948	0.542117	46510.28	2.51837	1.29843295
148	2021	United States	USA	1.046862006	1.33641	0.004954	70248.63	4.69786	0.90390658
149	2021	Uruguay	URY	1.61529088	0.83995	1.046311	17313.19	7.74791	1.29830694
150	2021	Uzbekistan	UZB	-0.808077157	-0.1968	-0.2398	1983.065	10.8492	-1.3997523
151	2021	Vanuatu	VUT	-0.017598171	-0.55845	0.791273	2996.621	2.34328	0.6939553
152	2021	Vietnam	VNM	-0.285784245	0.27798	-0.1146	3756.489	1.83472	-1.3042051
153	2021	West Bank and Gaza	PSE	-0.738599837	-0.76679	-1.83927	3663.969	1.23748	-1.110767
154	2021	Zambia	ZMB	-0.753424048	-0.81693	0.060216	1137.344	22.0212	-0.3669986
155	2021	Zimbabwe	ZWE	-1.257896781	-1.24293	-1.02678	1773.92	98.5461	-1.1369342